

Rendering of the task team work on driving GCM selection

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Big thank to the « EURO-CORDEX task team on GCM selection » for their helpful work

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Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 : towards a « better-built » GCM-RCM matrix

- A necessary sub-sampling
 - Ensemble ScenarioMIP CMIP6 (50 GCMs, 8 SSPs, 10 membres) → 4.000 runs (+ Large-Ens)
 - Ensemble Med-CORDEX-CMIP5 (7 GCMs, 11 RCMs, 3 RCPs, 1 member) → 19 runs
 - Filling the matrix is unaffordable (44.000 runs → how many real years ?!)
- Main drawbacks of current matrices
 - Unbalanced towards some GCMs or RCMs
 - Bad coverage of the range of possibilities
- Main objectives
 - Make our ensemble a more reliable source of information
 - Better built the matrix wrt clear scientific objectives
 - Stop the « ensemble of opportunity » approach
 - Improve, clarify and document the GCM selection procedure
 - Make it easier to complete statistically a posteriori (e.g. emulators)
- Setting of the « Med-CORDEX Task Team of driving GCM selection » (march 2022)
 - Collect the Med-CORDEX modelling group plans
 - Contribution to the EURO-CORDEX GCM selection task team
 - Adapt the EURO-CORDEX machinery for the MED domain

Selection criteria : 4 families

ScenarioMIP
All CMIP6 GCM runs

Data
Availability

GCM
Plausibility

GCM future
response **Diversity**

GCM
Independence

Data Availability to drive RCMs

- 1950-2100 : historical + 2 SSPs (ssp126, ssp370), 1 member min.
- Variables 3D, model levels, freq. 6-hr : ua, va, ta, hus, psl
- SST (tos), SIC (siconc), AOD (od550aer), freq. Monthly minimum
- Data « FAIR » (ESGF)
- Last update : 16 May 2022

- Total #GCM with at least 2 SSPs on ESGF : 62

- **#GCM with forcings for RCM for SSP126 and SSP370 : 18**

```
# All GCMs (62)
ACCESS-CM2 (3)
ACCESS-ESM1-5 (4)
AWI-CM-1-1-MR (1)
AWI-ESM-1-1-LR (1)
BCC-CSM2-MR (1)
BCC-ESM1 (3)
CAMS-CSM1-0 (2)
CAS-ESM2-0 (1)
CESM2 (8)
CESM2-FV2 (1)
CESM2-WACCM (3)
CESM2-WACCM-FV2 (1)
CIesm (1)
CMCC-CM2-HR4 (1)
CMCC-CM2-SR5 (1)
CMCC-ESM2 (2)
CNRM-CM6-1 (6)
CNRM-CM6-1-HR (1)
CNRM-ESM2-1 (5)
CanESM5 (50)
CanESM5-CanOE (6)
E3SM-1-0 (1)
E3SM-1-1 (1)
E3SM-1-1-ECA (1)
EC-Earth3 (8)
EC-Earth3-AerChem (2)
EC-Earth3-CC (1)
EC-Earth3-Veg (6)
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR (1)
FGOALS-f3-L (1)
FGOALS-g3 (2)
FIO-ESM-2-0 (3)
GFDL-CM4 (1)
GFDL-ESM4 (2)
GISS-E2-1-G (10)
GISS-E2-1-G-CC (1)
GISS-E2-1-H (4)
GISS-E2-2-G (1)
HadGEM3-GC31-LL (3)
HadGEM3-GC31-MM (2)
IITM-ESM (1)
INM-CM4-8 (1)
INM-CM5-0 (5)
IPSL-CM5A2-INCA (1)
IPSL-CM6A-LR (11)
IPSL-CM6A-LR-INCA (1)
KACE-1-0-G (2)
KIOST-ESM (1)
MCM-UA-1-0 (2)
MIROC6 (3)
MIROC-ES2L (10)
MPI-ESM1-2-HR (2)
MPI-ESM1-2-LR (30)
MPI-ESM1-2-HAM (3)
MRI-ESM2-0 (5)
NESM3 (2)
NorCPM1 (1)
NorESM2-LM (3)
NorESM2-MM (1)
SAM0-UNICON (1)
TaiESM1 (1)
UKESM1-0-LL (19)
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# RCM forcing, ssp126, ssp370 (18)
ACCESS-CM2 (3)
ACCESS-ESM1-5 (2)
AWI-CM-1-1-MR (0)
AWI-ESM-1-1-LR (0)
BCC-CSM2-MR (0)
BCC-ESM1 (0)
CAMS-CSM1-0 (0)
CAS-ESM2-0 (0)
CESM2 (1)
CESM2-FV2 (0)
CESM2-WACCM (0)
CESM2-WACCM-FV2 (0)
CIesm (0)
CMCC-CM2-HR4 (0)
CMCC-CM2-SR5 (1)
CMCC-ESM2 (1)
CNRM-CM6-1 (0)
CNRM-CM6-1-HR (0)
CNRM-ESM2-1 (1)
CanESM5 (3)
CanESM5-CanOE (0)
E3SM-1-0 (0)
E3SM-1-1 (0)
E3SM-1-1-ECA (0)
EC-Earth3 (2)
EC-Earth3-AerChem (0)
EC-Earth3-CC (0)
EC-Earth3-Veg (3)
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR (0)
FGOALS-f3-L (0)
FGOALS-g3 (0)
FIO-ESM-2-0 (0)
GFDL-CM4 (0)
GFDL-ESM4 (0)
GISS-E2-1-G (0)
GISS-E2-1-G-CC (0)
GISS-E2-1-H (0)
GISS-E2-2-G (0)
HadGEM3-GC31-LL (0)
HadGEM3-GC31-MM (0)
IITM-ESM (0)
INM-CM4-8 (0)
INM-CM5-0 (0)
IPSL-CM5A2-INCA (0)
IPSL-CM6A-LR (6)
IPSL-CM6A-LR-INCA (0)
KACE-1-0-G (0)
KIOST-ESM (0)
MCM-UA-1-0 (0)
MIROC6 (1)
MIROC-ES2L (10)
MPI-ESM1-2-HR (2)
MPI-ESM1-2-LR (30)
MPI-ESM1-2-HAM (0)
MRI-ESM2-0 (0)
NESM3 (0)
NorCPM1 (0)
NorESM2-LM (1)
NorESM2-MM (1)
SAM0-UNICON (0)
TaiESM1 (1)
UKESM1-0-LL (3)
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Plausibility : remove unrealistic driving GCMs

- Global climate criteria
 - ECS/TCR
 - Global metrics (incl. past trends)
- Euro-Mediterranean large-scale atmospheric forcings
 - Large-scale structures : Jet stream position
 - Variability : weather regimes, cyclone tracks
- Other relevant forcings for the Mediterranean region
 - Near-Atlantic SST, ~~Baltique SST~~, Black SST, Mediterranean SST
 - ~~Sea ice cover~~
 - Natural and anthropogenic aerosols
 - **Near-Atlantic surface ocean characteristics: T, S, SSH**

EURO-CORDEX criteria adapted to Med-CORDEX → 13 GCMs

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# RCM forcing, ssp126, ssp370 (13)
ACCESS-CM2 (3)
ACCESS-ESM1-5 (2)
AWI-CM-1-1-MR (0)
AWI-ESM-1-1-LR (0)
BCC-CSM2-MR (0)
BCC-ESM1 (0)
CAMS-CSM1-0 (0)
CAS-ESM2-0 (0)
CESM2 (1)
CESM2-FV2 (0)
CESM2-WACCM (0)
CESM2-WACCM-FV2 (0)
CIESM (0)
CMCC-CM2-HR4 (0)
CMCC-CM2-SR5 (1)
CMCC-ESM2 (1)
CNRM-CM6-1 (0)
CNRM-CM6-1-HR (0)
CNRM-ESM2-1 (1)
CanESM5 (3)
CanESM5-CanOE (0)
E3SM-1-0 (0)
E3SM-1-1 (0)
E3SM-1-1-ECA (0)
EC-Earth3 (2)
EC-Earth3-AerChem (0)
EC-Earth3-CC (0)
EC-Earth3-Veg (3)
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR (0)
FGOALS-f3-L (0)
FGOALS-g3 (0)
FIO-ESM-2-0 (0)
GFDL-CM4 (0)
GFDL-ESM4 (0)
GISS-E2-1-G (0)
GISS-E2-1-G-CC (0)
GISS-E2-1-H (0)
GISS-E2-2-G (0)
HadGEM3-GC31-LL (0)
HadGEM3-GC31-MM (0)
IITM-ESM (0)
INM-CM4-8 (0)
INM-CM5-0 (0)
IPSL-CM5A2-INCA (0)
IPSL-CM6A-LR (6)
IPSL-CM6A-LR-INCA (0)
KACE-1-0-G (0)
KIOST-ESM (0)
MCM-UA-1-0 (0)
MIROC6 (1)
MIROC-ES2L (10)
MPI-ESM1-2-HR (2)
MPI-ESM1-2-LR (30)
MPI-ESM-1-2-HAM (0)
MRI-ESM2-0 (0)
NESM3 (0)
NorCPM1 (0)
NorESM2-LM (1)
NorESM2-MM (1)
SAM0-UNICON (0)
TaiESM1 (1)
UKESM1-0-LL (3)
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Diversity of the projected futures to explore uncertainties

To Be Discussed

- Global climate
 - Diversity of the global climate response (TCR)

- Mediterranean climate
 - Change in regional near-surface temperature
 - Change in advected humidity
 - Change in relevant large-scale pattern: Jet stream position, weather regimes, cyclone tracks, polar vortex strength, tropical amplification, arctic amplification
 - Change in other relevant forcings: North-Atlantic SST, Black SST, Med SST, aerosols, Near-Atlantic Ocean characteristics

- Define more specific risk-relevant storylines
 - Coastal sea level
 - Marine ecosystem
 - Focus on specific criteria (e.g. Summer warming or Near-Atlantic surface salinity change)

GCM	member	resolution calendar	MED Dtas JJA ssp370 [2.6 ; 6.3]°C 2071-2100 vs 1981-2010	MED Dtas DJF ssp370 [2.3 ; 4.9]°C 2071-2100 vs 1981-2010
CESM2	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.5	2.9
CMCC-CM2-SR5	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.6	3.3
CMCC-ESM2	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	?	?
CNRM-ESM2-1	r11i1p1f2	150km (gregorian)	4.5	3.1
EC-Earth3	r11i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	5.9	4.1
EC-Earth3-Veg	r12i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	5.3	3.6
IPSL-CM6A-LR	rXi1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	5.0	3.3
MIROC6	r11i1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	4.6	2.9
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r11i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	3.6	2.5
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	r11i1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	3.9	2.8
NorESM2-MM	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.2	2.4
TaiESM1	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	?	?
UKESM1-0-LL	r11i1p1f2	250km (360d)	6.3	4.9

The Med-CORDEX GCMxRCM matrix so far

Among the 13 available and plausible GCMs (with so far used criteria)

- 4/13 already chosen by the modelling groups, 3/13 in option, 6/13 not mentioned
- 4/13 have a very low spatial resolution and 1/13 has a 360 day calendar
- Some GCMs are not intrinsically independent

GCM	member	resolution calendar	MED Dtas JJA ssp370 [2.6 ; 6.3]°C 2071-2100 vs 1981-2010	MED Dtas DJF ssp370 [2.3 ; 4.9]°C 2071-2100 vs 1981-2010	CNRM-RCM6	ENEA-REG	CLMcom-GUF- CCLM5-0-9-NE MOMED12-3-6	ICTP-OGS-RegCM-ES	IPSL-RegIPSL
CESM2	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.5	2.9					
CMCC-CM2-SR5	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.6	3.3	?				
CMCC-ESM2	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	?	?					
CNRM-ESM2-1	r11i1p1f2	150km (gregorian)	4.5	3.1	X			?	
EC-Earth3	r11i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	5.9	4.1		X			
EC-Earth3-Veg	r12i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	5.3	3.6			X (ssp585)	?	
IPSL-CM6A-LR	rXi1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	5.0	3.3					?
MIROC6	r11i1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	4.6	2.9					
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r11i1p1f1	100km (gregorian)	3.6	2.5		X		?	
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	r11i1p1f1	250km (gregorian)	3.9	2.8					
NorESM2-MM	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	4.2	2.4	?			?	
TaiESM1	r11i1p1f1	100km (365d)	?	?					
UKESM1-0-LL	r11i1p1f2	250km (360d)	6.3	4.9					

Conclusions : Med-CORDEX GCM selection task team

- Work far from completed
- General procedure and yaml/github machinery is working

OPEN ISSUES – TO BE DISCUSSED

- Additional plausibility criteria to be decided, computed and implemented
- Diversity criteria : « maximum spread approach » or « storyline approach » ?
- How to match the selection procedure with the modelling group constraints ?
- Who want to contribute ? so far, Jesus Fernandez (U. Cantabria), Samuel Somot (CNRM), Erika Coppola (ICTP), Gabriel Jordà (IEO), Javier Soto-Navarro (U. Malaga), Alessandro Anav (ENEA)
- How to publish this work ?

- *Need to acknowledge that :*
 - *Even if smarter, the new Med-CORDEX ensemble will remain relatively small*
 - *Any GCM selection exercise is subjective*

Independence : favor GCM intrinsic diversity

- Structural independence
 - Institutionnal democracy (Leduc et al. 2016)
 - Number of common components (J. Boe)
- Similarity independence
 - Similarity in a posteriori behaviour (Brunner et al. 2020)

EURO-CORDEX choice: 9 GCMs

RCM forcing, ssp126, ssp370 (9)
 CESM2 (1)
 CMCC-CM2-SR5 (1)
 CNRM-ESM2-1 (1)
 EC-Earth3-Veg (3)
 IPSL-CM6A-LR (6)
 MIROC6 (1)
 MPI-ESM1-2-HR (2)
 NorESM2-MM (1)
 UKESM1-0-LL (3)

RCM forcing, ssp126, ssp370 (9)
~~ACCESS-CM2 (3)~~
~~ACCESS-ESM1-5 (2)~~
 AWI-CM-1-1-MR (0)
 AWI-ESM-1-1-LR (0)
 BCC-CSM2-MR (0)
 BCC-ESM1 (0)
 CAMS-CSM1-0 (0)
 CAS-ESM2-0 (0)
CESM2 (1)
 CESM2-FV2 (0)
 CESM2-WACCM (0)
 CESM2-WACCM-FV2 (0)
 CIESM (0)
 CMCC-CM2-HR4 (0)
CMCC-CM2-SR5 (1)
~~CMCC-ESM2 (1)~~
 CNRM-CM6-1 (0)
 CNRM-CM6-1-HR (0)
CNRM-ESM2-1 (1)
~~CanESM5 (3)~~
 CanESM5-CanOE (0)
 E3SM-1-0 (0)
 E3SM-1-1 (0)
 E3SM-1-1-ECA (0)
~~EC-Earth3 (2)~~
 EC-Earth3-AerChem (0)
 EC-Earth3-CC (0)
EC-Earth3-Veg (3)
 EC-Earth3-Veg-LR (0)
 FGOALS-f3-L (0)
 FGOALS-g3 (0)
 FIO-ESM-2-0 (0)
 GFDL-CM4 (0)
 GFDL-ESM4 (0)
 GISS-E2-1-G (0)
 GISS-E2-1-G-CC (0)
 GISS-E2-1-H (0)
 GISS-E2-2-G (0)
 HadGEM3-GC31-LL (0)
 HadGEM3-GC31-MM (0)
 IITM-ESM (0)
 INM-CM4-8 (0)
 INM-CM5-0 (0)
 IPSL-CM5A2-INCA (0)
IPSL-CM6A-LR (6)
 IPSL-CM6A-LR-INCA (0)
 KACE-1-0-G (0)
 KIOST-ESM (0)
 MCM-UA-1-0 (0)
MIROC6 (1)
~~MIROC-ES2L (10)~~
 MPI-ESM1-2-HR (2)
~~MPI-ESM1-2-LR (30)~~
 MPI-ESM1-2-HAM (0)
 MRI-ESM2-0 (0)
 NESM3 (0)
 NorCPM1 (0)
~~NorESM2-IM (1)~~
 NorESM2-MM (1)
 SAM0-UNICON (0)
~~TaiESM1 (1)~~
 UKESM1-0-LL (3)

The EURO-CORDEX GCM selection so far

- Sobolowski et al. 2023, <https://www.zenodo.org/record/7673400>
- 9 GCMs available for 4 SSPs, plausible and independant (same as Med-CORDEX)
- Final selection : 6 GCMs for future diversity and practical reasons

GCM name	Run	Marks/Criteria	TCR Plausible range (1.2K-2.4K)
NorESM2-MM ¹⁵	r1i1p1f1	1/17	1.33
MIROC6 ¹⁶	r1i1p1f1	1/20	1.55
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r1i1p1f1	1/20	1.66
CNRM-ESM2-1	r1i1p1f2	1/19	1.86
CESM2 ¹⁷	r1i1p1f1	1/18	2.06
CMCC-CM2-SR5 ¹⁵	r1i1p1f1	1/15	2.09
IPSL-CM6A-LR ¹⁸	r1i1p1f1	2/16	2.32
EC-Earth3-Veg ²⁰	r1i1p1f1	2/15	2.62
UKESM1-0-LL ²¹	r1i1p1f2	2/19	2.79

Driving GCM / run	Institution / RCM						
	CNRM / ALADIN6x	CLMcom / COSMO - CLM	HCLIMcom / HCLIM43 - ALADIN	KNMI / RACMO23E	GERICS / REMO	CUNI,ICTP / RegCM	AUTH, CESAM... / WRF
NorESM2-MM / r1i1p1f1	X			X		X	X
MIROC6 / r1i1p1f1		X	X		X		
MPI-ESM1-2-HR / r1i1p1f1		X			X	X	X
CNRM-ESM2-1 / r1i1p1f2	X		X	X		X	
CMCC-CM2-SR5 / r1i1p1f1	X	X					X
EC-Earth3-Veg / r1i1p1f1			X	X	X	X	

Plausibility : remove unrealistic driving GCMs

Performance-based sub-selection of CMIP6 GCMs for risk assessment in Europe

Large-scale criteria only:

models remain in the sub-selection: ACCESS-CM2, BCC-CSM2-MR, CESM2, CESM2-WACCM, CNRM-CM6-1, CNRM-CM6-1-HR, CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3, EC-Earth3-Veg, GFDL-CM4, GFDL-ESM4, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, HadGEM3-GC31-MM, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, KACE-1-0-G, TaiEMS1 and UKESM1-0-LL. This sub-selection from the qualitative assessment can

Availability+Large-scale+MED region criteria

- ACCESS-CM2
- CESM2
- CNRM-ESM2-1
- EC-Earth3
- EC-Earth3-Veg
- MPI-ESM1-2-HR
- TaiESM1
- UKESM1-0-LL

Model diversity : the storyline approach

Smart selecting the final GCMs: application-relevant storylines

Storylines for Wintertime large-scale circulation change in CMIP5 GCM (2070-2100 vs 1960-1990, RCP8.5, NDJFMA)

Wintertime Mediterranean precipitation change (mm/j/K, 2070-2100 vs 1960-1990, RCP8.5, NDJFMA)

